

The Concept of the Due Diligence Procedure as the Modern Auditing and Consulting Services

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Abstract

This paper presents the concept of the Due Diligence procedure as modern auditing and consulting services. Conducting the Due Diligence involves the investment research implementation. The results of this research are the identification of risks that can have influence on a proposed capital market transaction, and the design of risk management techniques. The authors note one important applied problem — currently there are no professional auditing standards and methodological recommendations in the Uzbekistan legislation which regulate the process of organization and conducting of the Due Diligence procedure that accompanies auditing services.

The objectives of this article are to synthesize the results of earlier studies and to determine the key elements of the concept which is needed to develop the working techniques of conducting the Due Diligence in the Republic of Uzbekistan. In this paper the tasks are determined as the presentation of an algorithm for risk assessment in the Due Diligence procedure, the proposal of the main provisions of standards or methodological recommendations for the Due Diligence services, the formation of the glossary of terms for the purposes of developing of the working techniques of the Due Diligence. The relevance of the topic is determined by the necessity of the innovative development of theoretical and methodological bases of auditing activities in the Republic of Uzbekistan. The conditions for further improvement of professional practices should be made to provide high-level auditing and consulting services as well as other auditing services in order to meet present day's information needs of capital owners, who have to make decisions on investing in constantly changing and highly risky economic environment.

Keywords: auditing activities; auditing; consulting; auditing related services; Due Diligence; risks; investment.

Introduction

Auditing in Uzbekistan, like other professional fields, continues to develop. Development is constantly determined changing conditions of a market economy. With the emergence of new processes and phenomena in the Uzbekistan capital market, new needs of users of financial information for more progressive types of audit and consulting services. Thus, in order to meet the latest market challenges, audit and consulting professionals are required to respond quickly to offer investors modern developments and effective professional services. In this regard, both the development of practical activities and the improvement of the theoretical and methodological foundations themselves are important as a basis and guide for the implementation of professional services in the field of auditing and consulting.

Among such services, the due diligence procedure is currently gaining popularity. during which investment research is carried out to identify the risks of a proposed transaction with capital and develop competent measures to manage them. It should be noted that over the past 10 years, topic under study number of publications number of Uzbekistan scientists has increased significantly. The works of Yu.N. deserve great attention. Paradaev M.Q. [1], Guzov Iu. N., Savenkova N.D.[2], A. Chelyshev [3].

However, today for scientists, engaged in studying problems in the field audit, accounting, economic analysis, and specialists carrying out audit and consulting activities, issues remain relevant regarding the development clear and practical methodology due diligence, meeting the requirements of modern economic conditions and the needs users of accounting and analytical and other financial information, creating a standard or methodological recommendations for carrying out the procedure under study, searching for new methods for conducting analytical procedures, in particular identification, analysis and assessment risks to ensure the implementation of effective investment projects. The authors of this article previously published the results of a detailed comparative analysis of due diligence and audit procedures in order to determine criteria for classification the procedure under study in the audit system activities and the formulation of the author's definition of service [4]. Taking into account the fact, that due diligence is a relatively new species agreed upon procedures, it seems to us it is important to synthesize the findings and formulate the concept of the procedure due diligence as a modern audit and consulting service. However, in the article presentation tasks are also defined algorithm for conducting a risk assessment procedure within the framework of due diligence, as proposed the main provisions of the standard or guidelines for the provision of services, according to formation of a glossary of

terms for purposes development of a working methodology for due diligence. Let's consider the author's proposed concept of the due diligence procedure.

When developing the concept, the authors proceeded from the assumption that currently there is an objective need for the innovative development of theoretical and methodological fundamentals of auditing in the Uzbekistan, in creating conditions for further improvement of professional practices to provide related and other audit services, which will improve the quality of audit and consulting services provided services on par with audits for compliance purposes modern information needs capital owners making decisions by its investment in constantly changing and risk-prone conditions of the economic space. P.P. Baranov and A.A. Shaposhnikov in his work drew attention to the need “protecting society and the economy from information risk in decision making” [7]. It is also worth noting that valuable thoughts about further directions for the development of theory and methodology of auditing activities, improving the quality of auditing and consulting services are disclosed in the article by M.V. Melnik and V.Ya. Sokolov [8].

Thus, the assumption formulated in the article represents a certain guiding principle for the development working methodology for conducting agreed audit and consulting due diligence services for uzbek professional practice.

When considering a potential capital transaction, due diligence parties should be highlighted: a working group of experts, an investor, a third party. All author's definitions that apply for the working methodology of due diligence are given in the glossary of terms (Table 1).

Within the framework of the concept of the procedure under study we will also highlight the following subjects, objects and processes: 1) investor; 2) working group of experts; 3) third party - owners and management of the target company; 4) proposed capital transaction; 5) due diligence procedure; 6) interaction between the investor and the owners and management of the target company for the purpose of supporting a capital transaction; 7) interaction between the investor and the working group experts on the issue of conducting due diligence in relation to the target company and the implementation of a capital transaction; 8) interaction working group of experts with owners and management of the target company to carry out due diligence procedures.

Table 1

Glossary of terms of the author's due diligence methodology

№	Term	Definition of term
	Due diligence	An audit-related service performed in agreement with the potential investor in the form of a

		comprehensive examination of the proposed transaction as part of the process making a decision on a less risky investment of capital in order to preserve it and increase in the future
	Working group experts	A group of specialists participating in investment research in the form of due diligence: auditors, tax consultants, financial analysts, actuaries, appraisers, lawyers, marketers, environmental specialists, programmers
	Accounting due diligence	A detailed study of the target company's accounting system, identifying, assessment and analysis of risks in the process of generating accounting data in registers, in reporting process
	Financial due diligence	A detailed study of the processes of financial planning and forecasting activities, identification, assessment and analysis of financial resource management risks target companies
	Tax due diligence	Detailed study of the tax accounting system of the target company, identification, assessment and analysis of tax risks associated with existing or potential tax obligations
	Legal due diligence	Detailed research, identification, assessment and analysis of risks to the legitimacy of a legal entity status and economic activities of the target company
	Managerial due diligence	A detailed study of the effectiveness of the organization's employees, identifying, assessment and analysis of risks associated with investments in human capital
	Marketing due diligence	Detailed research, identification, assessment and analysis of risks associated with the occupation position of the organization in various markets, analysis of competitive advantages
	Ecological due diligence	Detailed research, identification, assessment and analysis of risks associated with implementation environmental protection programs, addressing health issues and environmental safety
	Informational due diligence	Detailed research, identification, assessment and analysis of operating risks information systems to support the activities of the target company

Due diligence agreement	Agreement for the provision of due diligence services concluded between an audit and consulting company, an investor and a third party
Investor	The initiator who has entered into an agreement for the provision of due diligence services, according to the results of which will receive a comprehensive report on current and potential risks for implementation of the planned capital transaction in relation to the target company
Target company	A company in respect of which an investment study is being conducted by an auditing and consulting company in the form of due diligence
Third party	Owners and management of the target company agreeing on the terms of the investment research
Complex due diligence report	A summary report compiled from individual reports prepared by working group based on the results of the planned procedures for due diligence directions, reflecting general conclusions about the state of the company's goals, information about current and potential risks affecting the implementation proposed capital transaction, recommendations and proposals for management identified risks in order to preserve and increase capital in the future
Risk	A probabilistic event assessed under conditions of uncertainty that can provide quantitative (financial) and (or) qualitative (non-financial) nature) influence on the result of making an investment decision on an investment capital, as well as the possibility of its preservation and increase in the future [9]
List of risks	A risk identification tool that allows detailed description of each identified risk
Identification risk	The process of identifying and classifying risk
Risk Analysis	The process of establishing risk parameters: probability of risk and financial effect Risk
Risk assessment	Determining the level of risk based on established parameters using a matrix risks

	Risk Matrix	A tool for expert qualitative assessment of identified risk, based on its parameters (probability of risk and financial effect of risk) for a specific direction of activity of the target company when conducting due diligence
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Within the framework of the proposed concept, due diligence as a professional audit and consulting service is defined three aspects: accounting, auditing, analytical. The accounting aspect implies that the data of the accounting system and the accounting (financial) system should be considered as the basis for carrying out procedures reporting. The audit aspect is in the similarity of testing methods events. The analytical aspect determines the nature of the procedures carried out within due diligence. It seems to the authors that the implementation analytical procedures in the process of implementing due diligence should be carried out according to eight areas: accounting due diligence, financial due diligence, tax due diligence, legal due diligence, managerial due diligence, marketing due diligence, information due diligence, environmental due diligence. Definitions of due diligence areas are given above (see Table 1). The article demonstrates a diagram of key directions and procedures that are optimal for conducting a full-fledged investment study. As noted at the beginning of the article, due diligence is currently gaining popularity in the uzbek audit and consulting industry practice. This fact is due to the strengthening investment processes in the global economy. At the same time, the results of due diligence are aimed at reducing risks investment, which is very important for the uzbek capital market. Taking into account the fact that by law this procedure is Uzbekistan is not regulated, auditing and consulting companies show creativity when performing investment research. There is a common opinion there are currently no uzbek specialists in conducting due diligence, which again confirms the need to develop a universal working methodology for due diligence for uzbek professional practice with for the purpose of supporting capital transactions. According to the authors of the article, the due diligence procedure should be based on modern accounting principles - the principles of actuarial ideology. Within the framework of actuarial accounting ideology involves the implementation of the principles of ethics and orientation towards the formation fair value of the target company in the future. These principles are largely determined by the needs of users in forecasting and identifying risks for companies in modern conditions of the global economy. The ethical principles that should be followed be guided by a working group of experts when performing due diligence regarding financial and non-financial information target companies are: honesty, objectivity, professional competence,

integrity, confidentiality, professional behavior. Orientation principle for the future is to form a working a group of experts forecasting and analytical information basis for creating a future value of the target company.

Systematic and risk-based approaches. System the approach involves the implementation of procedures a working group of experts consisting of specialists from different fields, which ensures complexity in conducting due diligence. The risk-based approach allows us to identify and focus the attention of experts on the most risky areas of activity of the target company, identify, analyze, assess risks and make proposals for their management.

The list of risks is compiled based on the due diligence risk classification [9]. Using this tool, current and potential risks, which allows the working group experts systematize information about existing threats to the proposed transaction with capital. The second tool - the risk matrix - allows you to give a qualitative assessment of the identified risks based on the parameters established during the identification process. Based on the assessment results the level of risk may be as follows values: minor (M), acceptable (A) and critical (C). Below is described in more detail author's algorithm for assessing identified risks.

Within the framework of the author's concept, risk assessment carried out according to a certain algorithm, which consists of four steps .

First, the probability of the identified risk (p) is established. Determination of the risk probability parameter is carried out by expert means. To assess the likelihood of risk, the following criteria are proposed (Table 2).

The established percentage value of the risk probability indicator corresponds to a numerical value from 1 to 5 in the risk matrix. Next, the level of materiality is determined (m). Let us introduce an assumption: as m it is proposed to take the value of the balance sheet currency indicator of the target company, since in the event of the realization of a risk with a financial effect exceeding a value equal to the sum of all assets, the company under analysis will cease to exist in the foreseeable future. Then the financial parameter is determined risk effect (f). To determine the specified parameter, experts are asked to be guided by the criteria presented in Table. 3. Estimated value of financial effect risk also corresponds to a numerical value from 1 to 5 in the risk matrix.

After determining the risk probability indicators and the financial effect of the risk, the working group experts must multiply obtained numerical values of indicators risk matrix and calculate the final score (a). To determine the final assessment of the identified risk, you should use formula:

$$a = pf$$

where:

a -is the final assessment of the identified risk;

p - numerical value of risk probability according to the risk matrix;
 f - is the numerical value of the financial effect of the risk according to the risk matrix.

The calculated products of the established parameters correspond to the intersections of coordinates in the risk matrix.

Table 2

Criteria for assessing the degree of probability of risk occurrence

Probability of risk (p)	Meaning indicator, %	Numeric value risk matrix indicator, conditional meaning
Most likely, the risk event will not occur	$p \leq 20$	1
The probability of a risk event occurring is below average	$20 < p \leq 40$	2
The probability of a risk event occurring is average	$40 < p \leq 60$	3
The probability of a risk event occurring is above average	$60 < p \leq 80$	4
The risk event will occur with a high degree of probability	$80 < p$	5

Table 3

Criteria for assessing the financial effect of risk

Financial effect of risk (f)	The calculated value of the indicator, thousand sums	Numerical value of the matrix indicator risks, conditional value
Irrelevant	$f \leq 0,25m$	1
Acceptable	$0,25m < f \leq 0,5m$	2
Essential	$0,5m < f \leq 0,75m$	3
Limit	$0,75m < f \leq m$	4
Catastrophic	$m < f$	5

Table 4**Criteria for the final assessment of the level of an identified risk event**

Estimated level of risk	Corresponding estimates, conditional value
Minor (M)	1-4
Acceptable (A)	5-10
Critical (C)	12-25

To understand the proposed algorithm Let's give an example of calculating the risk level assessment using a risk matrix. Thus, using the risk matrix it is proposed assess the level of identified threats proposed capital transaction (Table 5).

The implementation of any event requires a clear and understandable action plan. Having a plan allows you to understand the main tasks that are expressed in specific stages of the overall process, as well as the main goal, in other words, the end result that planned. Currently, economists at project development uses various planning methods. One of the modern methods is the construction of road maps. Road the card provides control based on application of the Deming cycle, or PDCA (PlanDo-Check-Act, or “Plan-Do-Check-Act”) [13].

Table 5**Calculation of assessment of the level of identified risks**

№	Description of the identified risk	Probability of risk (p), conditional meaning	Financial risk effect (f), conditional meaning	Final grade (a), conditional meaning	Level risk
1	Accounts receivable there will be no clients of the target company repaid on time, will become doubtful and will written off as a loss	4	3	12	C
2	Issued by the target company	5	2	10	A

	loans will not be repaid in accordance with the contract deadlines, the target company will not receive interest on loans issued				
3	As a result of cost reduction demand for production from buyers will decrease	2	2	4	M

Within the framework of the article, it seems relevant to us to propose the wording of the provisions professional auditing standard (or methodological recommendations), and also a glossary of terms for the purpose of developing a working due diligence methodology. Owners of capital, making decisions about it investment as part of the implementation of an investment project, they feel the need to receive high-quality transaction support services, because any transaction is subject to risk financial losses. Providers of services that allow assessing the current state and making forecasts for investment projects, auditing and consulting companies are currently performing. In order to provide a high-level professional service, auditing and consulting companies are improving in practical activities that allow you to meet the challenges constantly changing and subject to risks conditions of the Uzbekistan capital market. Together with However, economic conditions in the Uzbekistan create a field for the innovative development of theoretical and methodological foundations, as well as formation of new areas of activity in the field of audit and consulting, which contributes to improving service delivery practices. One of the modern audit and consulting services in Uzbekistan, popular among investors, becomes due diligence. Target procedures - to establish and assess existing and potential risks of the proposed capital transactions, suggest methods for minimization and prevention of identified investment threats. Today, auditing and consulting companies carry out the due diligence procedure in different ways; there is no universal working methodology, specific implementation algorithm, special standard or methodological recommendations for implementation. From here many questions arise, the answers to which are

ambiguous: which specialists must provide a service, what analytical procedures should be carried out, how to identify risks, how to analyze and evaluate them, how to systematize the results obtained during investment research and present them to the investor? This article formulates the author's concept of due diligence as a modern audit and consulting service. A convenient evaluation algorithm is proposed risks in the process of due diligence.

The provisions of the standard (methodological recommendations) and a glossary of terms are formulated, containing the author's interpretations. Issues requiring further research include the identification of effective analytical procedures to identify risks, as well as the search for advanced risk assessment tools and convenient methods for their management. Author also consider the problem of developing a special report form based on the results of due diligence. The question of the degree of detail of information about risks remains open, to be included in the report, because the investor as the main user of the document must make an independent decision based on it less risky investment.

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